

Study on selective sorption of ^{137}Cs on Al-substituted calcium silicate hydroxy hydrate

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Manuscript received 16 February 2000, revised 23 November 2000, accepted 24 February 2001

Sorption properties have been investigated by radiometric (tracer) technique at room temperature for aluminium substituted calcium silicate hydroxy hydrate, known as tobermorite. The ^{137}Cs selectivity has been examined in presence of 1000 times concentrated solution of Na^+ , Ca^{2+} and Ba^{2+} . The results suggest that the title phase could be used for immobilization of radioactive cesium. Cation exchange reaction takes place mainly from edge and planar surface sites along with interlayer Ca^{2+} sites.

^{137}Cs is a hazardous isotope present in nuclear effluents. Because of its long half-life ($T_{1/2} = 30.2$ yrs) it is necessary to remove ^{137}Cs from radioactive effluents¹. Immobilization and solidification techniques work on the principle of trapping the waste within a solid matrix having high structural integrity so that the risk of leaching is minimized². The reports on cesium selectivity³ of Al-substituted tobermorite have revealed that this phase is a potential material for its application in immobilization of ^{137}Cs . The radiometric data on Cs uptake may also be useful to solve the complex mechanism of ion exchange and cation uptake reactions of tobermorites in particular and other calcium silicate minerals in general⁴. Solid state ^{27}Al and ^{29}Si magic angle spinning (MASNMR) spectroscopy of the sample has been used to determine the location of Al and Si in aluminosilicate materials. The substitution of aluminium for silicon in the tetrahedral coordination has been demonstrated with solid state ^{27}Al MASNMR⁵. Coordination of silicon can be determined by ^{29}Si MASNMR and that of aluminium by ^{27}Al MASNMR; thus it is possible to probe the nearest neighbour environment by MASNMR⁶.

Results and Discussion

The X-ray powder diffraction pattern of the hydrothermally synthesized calcium silicate hydrate matches in intensity and position with the JCPDS file⁷. It gives 22 reflections with d -values between 1.15 and 0.115 nm. The ^{137}Cs selectivity of the synthetic product was investigated by radiometric (tracer) technique which allows accurate measurements at very low concentrations (0.0001 N) of Cs^+ in the presence of excess of competing cation (0.1 M). ^{27}Al MASNMR spectroscopy of the synthetic tobermorites showed ^{27}Al chemical shifts at 60.30 (tetrahedral site) and at 24.59 ppm (octahedral site) from $[\text{Al}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]^{3+}$ as a reference. This assignment of ^{27}Al chemical shift to tetrahedral coordination is based on earlier investigations which showed that tetrahedrally coordinated aluminium resonates at approximately 50 ± 20 ppm⁸, while octahedrally coordinated

aluminium resonates at about 0 ± 10 ppm. ^{29}Si MASNMR provides quantitative information on the fractions of silicon present in different tetrahedral environments, Q^n , where n denotes the connectivity of the silicate tetrahedron ($0 \leq n \leq 4$) and Q denotes SiO_4 group. Thus Q^0 represents isolated tetrahedra, Q^1 chain end-group tetrahedra, Q^2 middle groups, Q^3 branching sites and Q^4 polymerisation of the Q^n building units. The substitutions of Si by Al in tetrahedra sites produce down-field shifts of $\approx 3 \rightarrow 5$ ppm/Al⁹. Al present in the tobermorite may substitute for bridging and non-bridging site giving rise to $Q^1(\text{OAl})$ and $Q^1(1\text{Al})$, $Q^2(\text{OAl})$ and $Q^2(1\text{Al})$. Al-substituting in non-bridging site is indicated by the peak due to $Q^1(1\text{Al})$ at -73.78 ppm¹⁰. Another peak at -63.73 ppm shows the presence of Q^0 site (monomer). Table 1 summarizes the data on selective uptake of ^{137}Cs by 0.2 and 6.1 wt% alumina-substituted tobermorite from pure and mixed cation solutions of $\text{Na}^+ + \text{Cs}^+$. Tobermorites substituted with 0.2 and 6.1 wt% alumina correspond to 0.0037 and 0.113 mole% of Al, respectively, in the tobermorite framework. The selectivity data can be expressed in terms of sorption percent (%) and selectivity coefficient (K_d). The sorption properties of Cs may be attributed to the crystallochemical incorporation of Cs in layered lattice framework of tobermorite¹¹. The examination of published thermodynamic and kinetic data on sorption of other alkali and alkaline earth cations indicate that the uptake in tobermorite is basically due to the ion exchange along with simultaneous precipitation of complex silicate species in the alkaline medium¹². The addition of different cations in the solution lowers the value of sorption % of cesium. From the data in Table 2 it has been noted that the Cs removal decreases in presence of larger cations like K^+ and Ba^{2+} , whereas in the presence of the smaller cations like Na^+ and Ca^{2+} the selective property of the tobermorite is significantly retained. The Cs^+ selectivity of the alumina-substituted tobermorite in the presence of other cation

Table 1. Sorption data of ^{137}Cs onto 0.2 wt% alumina-substituted tobermorite*

Initial counts/50 s = 1693 ± 20					
Wt of exch mg	Final count	Δ	D_t	% Cs removal	K_d ml g ⁻¹
0.0001 N Cs ⁺					
10	1570	123	1.07	7.26	463.67
20	1253	440	1.35	25.98	185.02
40	829	864	2.04	51.03	61.20
80	589	1104	2.87	65.20	21.74
100	397	1296	4.26	76.55	11.72
0.0001 N Cs ⁺ + 0.1 M Na ⁺					
10	1583	110	1.06	6.49	467.51
20	1298	395	1.30	23.33	191.67
40	1297	396	1.30	23.39	95.76
80	1187	506	1.42	29.88	43.82
100	1044	649	1.62	38.33	30.83
0.0001 N Cs ⁺ + 0.1 M Ba ²⁺					
10	1579	114	1.07	6.73	466.33
20	1251	442	1.35	26.10	184.73
40	1100	593	1.53	35.02	81.21
80	770	923	2.19	54.51	28.42
100	1009	684	1.67	40.40	29.79
0.0001 N Cs ⁺ + 0.1 M Cs ²⁺					
10	1609	86	1.05	5.07	475.19
20	1236	457	1.36	26.99	182.51
40	1230	463	1.37	27.34	90.81
80	1202	491	1.40	29.00	44.37
100	1170	523	1.44	30.89	34.55

* Δ = Initial Cs⁺ - final Cs⁺, K_d = distribution coefficient = $(C_0/C_e - 1) A/M$, C_0 = initial Cs, C_e = final Cs, A = vol. of soln. (ml), M = mass of the exch. (g), D_t = decontamination factor = initial Cs concn / final Cs concn % Cs removal = $\Delta \times 100/\text{initial Cs}$

Table 2. Sorption data of ^{137}Cs onto 6.1 wt% alumina-substituted tobermorite

Initial counts/50 s = 1693 ± 20					
Wt of exch mg	Final count	Δ	D_t	% Cs removal	K_d ml g ⁻¹
0.0001 N Cs ⁺					
10	1097	596	1.54	35.20	323.98
20	755	938	2.24	55.40	111.48
40	585	1108	2.89	65.44	43.19
80	507	1186	3.33	70.05	18.71
100	397	1296	4.26	76.55	11.72
0.0001 N Cs ⁺ + 0.1 M Na ⁺					
10	1509	184	1.12	10.86	445.65
20	1463	230	1.15	13.58	216.03
40	1185	508	1.42	30.08	87.49
80	981	712	1.72	42.05	36.21
100	954	739	1.77	43.65	18.17
0.0001 N Cs ⁺ + 0.1 M Ba ²⁺					
10	1392	300	1.21	17.72	411.10
20	1251	442	1.35	26.10	184.73
40	1100	593	1.53	35.02	81.21
80	769	924	2.20	54.57	28.38
100	694	999	2.43	59.60	20.49
0.0001 N Cs ⁺ + 0.1 M Ca ²⁺					
10	1254	439	1.35	25.93	370.34
20	1236	457	1.36	26.99	182.51
40	1230	463	1.37	27.34	90.81
80	1202	491	1.40	29.00	44.37
100	1093	600	1.54	35.44	32.27

* Explanation same as in Table 1

decreases¹³ in the order, Ba²⁺ > Na⁺ > Ca²⁺ > Mg²⁺ > Sr²⁺. From the values in Tables 1 and 2 it becomes clear that with increase in mole% of aluminium substitution for silicon in tobermorite the percent Cs removal increases. It increases from 7.25 to 35.23% in case of pure Cs solution and 6.50 to 10.88% for (Cs⁺ + Na⁺) mixed cationic solution. It also increases with increase in the wt. of the exchanger (mg). Thus, the exchanger can be effectively used for cesium removal from a mixture of cations. As such it could be a potential additive in cementitious materials for solidification and immobilization of cesium in industrial and radioactive waste effluents.

Experimental

The hydrothermal synthesis of the title phase was carried out from lime (CaO), silica (SiO₂) and alumina (Al₂O₃) in teflon coated pressure bombs at 175° using the reported method¹⁴. The Ca/(Si + Al) ratio was kept at 0.8. The product was characterized by chemical analysis and powder X-ray diffraction in the range 2 θ = 5 to 80° using Ni filtered Cu-K α (λ = 1.54 Å) radiations on a PW-1820 diffractometer. The morphology of the specimen was also examined¹⁵ under a Philips 420 TEM microscope. The solid state ²⁷Al and ²⁹Si magic angle spinning NMR (MASNMR) spectroscopy of tobermorite specimens was carried out using NMR spectrometer at I.I.Sc., Bangalore. ²⁷Al chemical shifts were recorded with respect to [Al(H₂O)₆]³⁺ as an external reference and ²⁹Si chemical shifts recorded with respect to tetramethylsilane. The spectra were recorded without any resolution enhancement. ¹³⁷Cs uptake and equilibrium studies were carried out¹⁶ on a GRS 2313-315 (ECI Ltd., India) gamma-ray spectrometer. 10–100 mg of the sample was equilibrated with mixed solution (5 ml) containing 0.0001 N Cs⁺ and 0.1 M of each of the cation, viz. Na⁺, Ca²⁺ and Ba²⁺ separately. The solution was spiked with tracer solution of ¹³⁷Cs and shaken well before adding to the exchanger; the initial counts were recorded for each of the triplicate sets. After addition of exchanger, the solutions were shaken to reach steady state and final gamma counts were recorded for each of the triplicate sets. The average of the three counts was taken as the final value. The spectrometer was calibrated with the three ¹³⁷Cs solutions.

Acknowledgement

The authors thankfully acknowledge the financial support from the Department of Atomic Energy, Government of India under its Boards of Research Nuclear Sciences program No. 36/391-G. They also thank Head, Department of Chemistry, Dr. H. S. Gour University for facilities, and to C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for the award of a research associateship to one of them (R.S.).

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